

STUDIES ON THE PHOTOCHEMICAL ACTIVITY OF MIXTURES OF VANADIC ACID AND TARTARIC ACID. PART III. INDUCED CIRCULAR DICHROISM IN VANADIC ACID SOL. PHOTOREDUCTION OF DICHROIC SOL BY TARTARIC ACID IN CIRCULARLY POLARISED LIGHT.

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Vanadic acid sol exhibits circular dichroism in the visible region on exposure to *d*- and *l*-circularly polarised light. The photoreduction of the dichroic sol by tartaric acid has been studied and differences have been obtained for the velocity of the reaction in *d*- and *l*-light.

Vanadic acid sol exhibits the phenomena of streaming anisotropy (Freundlich *et al*, *Koll. Chem.-Beih.*, 1915, 7, 195; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1924, 114, 161). The experiments of Weigert (*Naturwiss.*, 1928, 16, 163; *Z. physikal. Chem.*; 1929, B3, 377, 389; 1929, B4, 83) and Zocher and Coper (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1928, 132, 303, 313) on silver halide layers show that polarised light exerts an orienting influence on thin films, causing a transition from the isotropic to the anisotropic state. Ghosh *et al* (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 495, 617; *Kolloid Z.*, 1929, 86, 372) have shown that sols of vanadic acid, tungstic acid, chromic tungstate and ceric borate exhibit circular dichroism in ultraviolet, when they are exposed to *d*- and *l*-circularly polarised light, the anisotropy factor being negative and positive respectively. They have also found that, in photochemical reactions wherein these sols act as sensitisers or as oxidants, *l*-circularly polarised light gives a higher value for the reaction velocity than *d*-light. In a previous paper, the author has shown that, in the photocatalytic oxidation of tartaric acid by persulphate using circularly dichroic micelles obtained by the reduction of vanadic acid and *d*- or *l*-tartaric acid as catalyst, differences are obtained for the velocity of the reaction in *d*- and *l*-circularly polarised light (Rama Char, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 563).

In the present investigation, circular dichroism has been induced in vanadic acid sol by exposure to *d*- and *l*-light. The influence of *d*- and *l*-light on the photoreduction of the dichroic sol has been studied.

Induced Dichroism.

Vanadic acid sol was prepared by the action of acetic acid on sodium metavanadate; the colour of the sol was between red and orange. The

p_n of the sol was measured electrometrically by the glass electrode. Such a sol has no circular dichroism, in the visible nor does it develop any on keeping in the dark for five hours. But on exposure of the freshly prepared sol to *d*- and *l*-circularly polarised visible light, it develops circular dichroism. The ellipticity measurements were made with the arrangement described in the Part II of this series (*loc. cit.*) The experimental results are given below. The ellipticity readings were correct to $\pm 0.02^\circ$.

TABLE I.

Conc. of vanadic acid sol (as V^5) = $0.10M$. Radiation = whole visible.
Intensity of exciting radiation = 7784 ergs. $p_n = 5.3$. Period of
excitation of sol = 5 hours.

Wave-length.	Length of soln.	Ellipticity developed on exposure to	
		<i>d</i> -light.	<i>l</i> -light.
5780Å	4 cm.	-0.15°	+0.30°
5460	3	-0.30	+0.60
5200	2	-0.90	-
4916	0.5	-0.25	-

The above table shows that when the sol is excited in (*i.e.* exposed to) *d*-circularly polarised light, it develops a negative ellipticity which has a very high value at 5200Å and 4916Å . On the other hand, excitation of the sol in *l*-light results in the development of positive ellipticity which has a high value at 5460Å . No optical rotation was found in both the cases. The dichroism that is developed does not change on keeping the sol for 24 hours.

Photoreduction.

Vanadic acid sol can be reduced by organic substances like tartaric acid, mandelic acid, etc., in visible light, vanadium being reduced from the pentavalent to the quadrivalent state: $V_2O_5 \rightarrow V_2O_4$. The colour change is from red or yellow to greenish black, blue or violet, depending upon the p_n .

The freshly prepared sol at $p_n 5.3$ was pre-excited (*i.e.* exposed to light before the reaction) in *d*- and *l*-light, and in each case the velocity of the reaction was found out in *d*- and *l*-light. Vanadic acid (as pentavalent vanadium) was estimated according to the method of Furman (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1925, 17, 314). There is no dark reaction at $p_n 5.5$, and the photochemical reaction is zero-molecular with respect to vanadic acid,

The results obtained for the velocity of the photoreduction are given below. dx/dt refers to the number of g. mols. transformed per minute. *d*-Tartrate is a mixture of *d*- and *l*-tartrates in equimolar proportions.

TABLE II.

Potassium tartrate = 0.10*M*. Radiation = whole visible. Vanadic acid sol = 0.05*M*. $p_H = 5.5$. Temp. = 25°. $I_{abs} = 1384$ ergs (in all cases). Period of excitation of sol = 5 hrs. Intensity of exciting radiation for sol = 7784 ergs.

Reductant.	Sol excited in <i>d</i> -light.	$dx/dt \times 10^5$		Sol excited in <i>l</i> -light.
		Reaction mixture exposed to <i>l</i> -light.	<i>d</i> -light.	
<i>d</i> -tartrate	2.78	2.22	2.08	2.50
<i>l</i> - "	2.73	2.18	2.08	2.50
<i>dl</i> - "	2.78	2.22	2.04	2.50
<i>r</i> - "	2.78	2.22	2.13	2.55

The results show that when the sol is pre-excited in *d*-light, the velocity of the photoreduction of the sol is greater in *d*-light than in *l*-light; the reverse is the case when the sol is pre-excited in *l*-light, the velocity in *l*-light being greater than that in *d*-light. These velocity results are of the same type whether the reductant used is *d*- or *l*- or *dl*- or racemic-tartrate. It is clear, therefore, that at $p_H 5.5$, tartaric acid acts only as an acceptor for vanadic acid. The quantum efficiency is of the order of 0.4 (mean value).

The differences in velocity are in accordance with the dichroism exhibited by the sol on excitation. It must be mentioned here that the dichroism of the sol is not changed on being mixed with tartrate, the final concentrations being the same. When the sol is excited in *d*-light, the ellipticity developed is negative, i.e. $\epsilon_d > \epsilon_l$ (where ϵ_d and ϵ_l are the molecular extinction coefficients of the sol in *d*- and *l*-light respectively) (Rama Char, *loc. cit.*) a larger fraction of the incident *d*-light is absorbed by the surface layer of the sol particles and therefore, the velocity in *d*-light is expected to be greater than that in *l*-light. On the other hand, the ellipticity of the sol excited in *l*-light is positive, i.e. $\epsilon_l > \epsilon_d$, and the velocity in *l*-light is expected to be greater than that in *d*-light. Table I shows that the excited sol exhibits circular dichroism in the yellow, green and blue regions. It has been experimentally found that vanadic acid sol undergoes photoreduction by tartaric acid in these regions.

Table III gives the results obtained for the velocity of the photo-reduction of the dichroic sol in unpolarised (ordinary) light.

TABLE III.

Radiation = unpolarised light. Other conditions same as in Table II.

Excitation of sol.	d-tartrate.	$\frac{dx}{dt} \times 10^5$.		
		l-tartrate.	dl-tartrate.	r-tartrate.
d-Circular	1'39	1'39	1'39	1'44
l. ,,	1'39	1'39	1'39	1'44

The velocity of the reaction in unpolarised light is independent of the nature of the excitation of the sol used and also independent of the reductant.

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